

The element extracted from lighting equipments that don't take discomfort from darkness

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Abstract

The light is the most important elements of lighting equipments, and the dark is the composition of the light. People have impressed anxiety and fear from darkness, that is root of the people emotion and common sense. (anxiety symptom of age clinic study group of anxiety and depression 1997)

I think anxiety and fear will effect for people afraid, that links with discomfort. When people had met with darkness, they have been impressed anxiety at first. The anxiety is non-targetable affective confusion from inner contradiction and natural emotion to danger. (anxiety symptom of age clinic study group of anxiety and depression 1997)

After that, people have been impressed by fear. The fear is more close to people than anxiety, because that is concrete and actual. (anxiety material of in the brain kaiya Hisanobu 1997)

So I think that the process which people have impressed anxiety and fear as they confronted with the darkness was that.

1. When people have been in the dark, they are blocked out their sight, they can't recognize the space, and feels anxiety from non-target affective confusion.
2. People are recollected fear from the anxiety to darkness through their experience.

Thus, anxiety is not permanent. And I had hypothesis as follows;

Fear is the result of anxiety. And fear makes afraid and discomfort. And then I could take the data that people are in more abstract to anxiety and in more concrete to fear.

From that data I could extract element of darkness with no fear and no afraid, because of giving the definition to emotion of anxiety and fear.

According to the hypothesis, Anxiety corresponds with abstraction word of emotion, and fear corresponds with concrete word of emotion. Finally I think it is available to designs of lighting fixtures brought from attractive of right and darkness.

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Research background

The lighting plan to put out "darkness" is generalized at modern Japanese night, and that seems to be daytime. The original function of "darkness" has can't be understood in that light space. The function of "darkness" is concerned with the autonomic nervous system that prepares the balance of the human body and it influences the parasympathetic that administers a rest. The autonomic nervous system is adjusted by the light through eyes. The exchange nerve that a human being acts actively functions in the time zone that is full of the light of the daytime. Sympathetic nervous system is the nerve becomes active at the time of the nervous condition. The function of the sympathetic nervous system is in such cases as "A pupil opens." "perspiration due to the strain of the mind" "the contraction of the muscle and the blood vessel" "dryness of the mouth" "The movement of the heart is made early." "rise in the blood pressure" "the repression of the gastroenteric function". It changes into the parasympathetic from the sympathetic nervous system when night comes and the color of the light that can be understood from the eye changes. A parasympathetic is the nerve becomes active during the sleep and the meal. The function of the internal organs is made to relax, and energy is made to recover. Lymphocytes increase by a parasympathetic's working in the predominance, and the immunity power rises, and has the power of resistance. The function of the parasympathetic does a function like "The number of times of the breathing is reduced." "A pulse is restrained." "The function of the heart is restrained." "Blood pressure falls down." "A digestion and excretion are suggested." In other words, a parasympathetic works in the predominance when it is opened from the condition that it relaxes and which feels the strain.

(<http://www.xylidentx.com/medical/fukukoukanshinkei/>)

While the light that a human being can act actively should be necessary in the daytime, "the mild darkness" that a human being can heal the fatigue of the daytime is looked for at night.

"Darkness" has important meaning against the Japanese culture. As for the Tea ceremony (fig.1) and the Noh play, (fig.2) the original space was produced by using "darkness" effectively. Then, it is considering that the original space is touching the people's emotion richly. As for Tatsuoki Nakajima . As for our predecessor, the daily space became art by manipulating an available light and a small quantity flame.

Figure 1: Japanese house where the Tea ceremony done

Figure 2: Noh play (<http://www2.city.taketa.oita.jp/kanko/topics/1151977376.html>)

That light is understood, and many Japanese who handed it down today are thought to be the rich race of the sensitivity of the light which it can be proud of in the world. It is mentioned. (The design of the lighting “あかり” Tatsuoki Nakajima 2000)

As for Miyamoto's "the research on the creation of the darkness space in the campus space". It is pointed out that recognition in "the darkness" in the modern daily life becomes weak. It is suggested that "darkness" is worthwhile as a non-daily life. It is mentioned.

It is considering that generally "darkness" gives the people anxiety and fear. But, according to Tsukahara as the contents which Jean-Jacques Rousseau wrote to "the Emil". "Rousseau, passed a graveyard in the school days, and the liver trial to bring the Bible from the church was given.

That church notices that it is fine with the church of the daytime at all the moment it listened to the laugh sound that could be heard from the light of the distant house and that though a church to see at night is dark unlike noon and it is the terrible object feels uneasy. Then, the first fear goes away like a lie. It is mentioned. (Why can a human being become a non-human being? Humi Tsukahara 2000.)

Like this, the way of thinking against "darkness" sometimes varies according to the existence of the individual understanding against "darkness". "Meaningless darkness" is a passive thing, and unpleasant. But, it doesn't feel the emotion of the unpleasantness from "meaningful darkness". Even if it felt an unpleasantness there before, as for that, it can feel the good point of comfortable feeling with makes interpretation possible. In a word, as for "darkness", from thinking that it is influencing an emotion such as fear and a worry by the individual understanding. A human being can think that an emotion against darkness can be controlled. The darkness of night is created newly. Then, "the darkness" has the intention that has been loved since the old days. It decides to be restored at modern night. That creates "the darkness" which the people desire in the value of the present day. Then, it thinks that it becomes the start when the people reconsider the value of darkness.

Purpose

The important element composes lighting equipments is light. Then, there is "darkness" behind the existence of the light. A human being has an emotion like "anxiety" "fear" against "darkness". That is being made a root-like emotion, and it is common to everyone (anxiety symptom of age clinic study group of anxiety and depression 1997) Then, it thinks that it is connected with the unpleasantness by the thing which can become the cause which gives it afraid. When a person meets it in "darkness", it thinks that the emotion that it happens first is "anxiety". It is the emotion which happens naturally when "anxiety" was emotional confusion with no object that it rises from the internal contradiction and it was put on the dangerous situation (anxiety symptom of age clinic study group of anxiety and depression 1997) Next, as for "fear" which it feels "fear" with, than "a worry", it becomes the thing which got clear. The object of "fear" is the concrete and realistic emotion which can be recognized clearly. (anxiety

material of in the brain kaiya Hisanobu 1997) As a process which it feels "anxiety" "fear" with when then a person meets it in "darkness" .

Then we got hypothesis as follows ;

1. When it goes into "darkness", the space can't be grasped from having sight interrupted of the object. It feels "worry" from the emotional confusion is not here.
2. Then we remind "fear" through the experience of "anxiety" faces "darkness" .

Therefore, "anxiety" is transient. "Fear" is thought to be the emotion that it has an influence more than "anxiety" and it is caused. Then, it is connected with the emotion of the unpleasantness that can terrible more. From the above, a person is abstract to "anxiety". It thinks that it can get the data that have a concrete emotion to "fear", and aims at verifying this hypothesis.

Method

The impression of "anxiety" and "the fear" that a human being has was researched by doing a questionnaire by the freedom description to verify the above hypothesis. (tab.1)

The image shows a questionnaire form with a title in Japanese: 「恐怖」と聞いてイメージする言葉を3つあげてください (Please list 3 words you imagine when you hear "fear"). Below the title are three empty rectangular boxes for writing answers.

Table 1: questionnaire.

The questionnaire which SD law was used for more than the word extracted than that result was made, and the degree of abstraction of the word was investigated. (tab.2)

次の言葉に対するイメージを五段階で評価してください

対人	抽象的						具体的
精神	抽象的						具体的
おぼけ	抽象的						具体的
夜	抽象的						具体的
変化	抽象的						具体的
地震	抽象的						具体的

Table 2: questionnaire

That result was made numerical value, and the existence of the significant difference in the degree of abstraction was confirmed by analyzing it by using the t-test from two words.

Experiment plan

Experiment cooperater

The number thirty people (man fifteen 15 woman)

Nationality Japanese, South Korean, Chinese and Brazilian

The average age 26.3 years old

1. I have each three impression for "the anxiety" and "the fear" enumerated by the freedom description. And, a language to use makes how to describe it a word or a sentence in Japanese. (fig.1)
2. A text analysis was done by using KH Coder relate with the result of 1. Furthermore, it was divided into the one of speech by the part, the appearance number of times was counted, a word was extracted.
3. It was extracted more than the result of 2. Questionnaire preparation (fig.2) by the SD law which moved an ingredient body to the two poles abstractly by using word, which the word which "a anxiety" was imaged from, "fear" were imaged from.
4. The result of 3.made numerical value. A t-test was done from each average. A difference in some thought between the words where it was remembered from "the anxiety" and "the fear" was investigated and analyzed.

Result

From the result of exp.2, an abstract word was extracted to the word "anxiety" was imaged. Then, a concrete word was extracted to the word which "fear" was imaged. (tab.3)

名詞	サ変名詞	形容動詞	副詞可能	未知語	タグ	動詞	形容詞	名詞B	名詞C										
映画	3	戦争	3	安定	1	夜	2	シャイニング	1	sf	1	後ずさる	1	暗い	1	おばけ	3	死	6
期間	2	仕事	1	危険	1	逃	1	おぼり	1	忘れ	1	忘れる	1	誤い	1	おばあさん	1	鬼	2
高所	2	失望	1	不安	1			ジェットコースター	1	慮す	1	慮す	1			やみ	1	音	1
殺人	2	信用	1					スクリーム	1									顔	1
事故	2	沈黙	1					ストーリー	1									血	1
子口	1	病気	1					ネットで個人情報を出させてしまう	1									黒	1
救急	1	浮気	1					恐怖の映画	1									病	1
呼び	1	分析	1					見えない	1										
売場	1	落下	1					現状を見てふと寝にかえる	1										
地震	1							高いところ	1										
落み	1							虫をとる	1										
独り	1							殺人鬼	1										
病院	1							社会主義国家	1										
未知	1							取り戻される	1										
無実	1							解わらない	1										
猛烈	1							親しい人の死	1										
幽霊	1							人間関係	1										
								赤から青	1										
								別人恐怖	1										
								希望なし	1										
								大切な物を失うこと	1										
								誰もいない家に帰ってきた時の2階の期間	1										
								電車の中	1										
								背筋が永る	1										
								怖い映画	1										
								方法なし	1										
								予測できない時	1										

Table 3: abstract word.

From the result of exp.4, a significant difference wasn't recognized in either of the words. But, as for the mean as for the word which "anxiety" was imaged, inclination to the minus was confirmed. Then, inclination from the word which "fear" is imaged to the plus can be confirmed. As that result, the tendency that it moved concretely was recognized from the word that "fear" was imaged from the word "worry". (tab.4)

t-検定: 等分散を仮定した2標本による検定		
	変数 1	変数 2
平均	-0.262222222	0.393333333
分散	1.971175452	1.940712695
観測数	450	450
プールされた分散	1.955944073	
仮説平均との差異	0	
自由度	898	
t	-7.031088184	
P(T<=t) 片側	2.02851E-12	
t 境界値 片側	1.646552238	
P(T<=t) 両側	4.05702E-12	
t 境界値 両側	1.962609172	

Table 4: t-test.

Consideration

It can think significant difference isn't recognized between either of the words. The meaning of the detailed word can be thought to do the origin in each person's context. But, as for last experiment,

the dispersion of the impression for the word was seen because a detailed setup wasn't done to each word and enumerated as a word. It could not think that some thought could be confirmed from that. As for the next investigation through questionnaire, the unification of the context for the word should be more necessary than the above consideration. But, in the result from questionnaire, the word "anxiety" is imaged from had more numbers of words to explain a concrete scene by the sentence than the word "fear" is imaged from. And there are many answers "Fear" faces a person more than "a anxiety", and thinks that it is understood that it is made to have a definite image from this as well.

Conclusion

"Light" and "darkness" have close relations to the light, and a human feeling and physical condition influence "light" and "darkness" closely, too. "Darkness" shows both the tendency of pleasure and the tendency of the unpleasantness by the way of catching it. From that, understanding from the position that a light is designed to "darkness" is deepened. As for that, the space of "darkness" where an emotion is expressive, proposing design. The importance is suggested that the element doesn't make it feel "darkness" with the unpleasantness is extracted. As for the unpleasantness it feels with "darkness", that "fear" is a cause we thought. When a human being lives, space to feel a charm and tranquility with "darkness", to produce. It thinks that it is to interrupt the matter that a rest has a human emotion from "the anxiety" to "fear" by the production of the light. It is effective to give the definition of the impression of "the anxiety" and "the fear" because of that. In this experiment, though a significant difference wasn't recognized "A anxiety" is abstract, and "fear" is concrete. It went to confirm the above tendency. When a future light is designed, this becomes the element that "darkness" is produced.

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